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Dr Ferreira (NF) is an Auxiliary Researcher at CIIMAR, experienced in applying different techniques at different organisational levels (from molecular to population) to understand the impacts of pollutants on ecosystems. NF's main focus is the application of 'Omics techniques to environmental and human toxicology based on Planetary Health principles. The results of his research have led to several practical outcomes that range from the application of new policies and measures to protect the environment and human populations to dissemination and co-working activities with schools, farmers and stakeholders, resulting in the solution of practical problems. NF has successfully obtained more than 3.5 M€ in grants and projects, received several awards and acted as a reviewer for different Funding programs.

ECOGOAL APP: A NEW TOOL FOR CITIZEN SCIENCE

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Abstract

Ecogoal is a citizen science app that empowers individuals to contribute to environmental research and conservation efforts. By gamifying its use, the app encourages users to actively use it and to acquire more knowledge about the main topics of the BEESNESS project. The app also includes educational components, providing users with information about local ecosystems, species identification guides, and updates on how their contributions are being used in scientific research. This educational aspect helps to increase public engagement with science and environmental issues. Using Ecogoal, students and other groups of people become “citizen scientists” who can share any event in the form of photos, video, audio, or writing. In addition, Ecogoal offers various projects that users can participate in, focusing on specific species, habitats, or environmental issues. This targeted approach allows researchers to gather data on particular areas of interest while engaging citizens in meaningful scientific work. The web-based app allows universal usage through different platforms, equipment, and operating systems. It is accessible to people of all ages and has an implementation of rules that protect each individual. This fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility towards other users and the environment. By leveraging common technology and citizen participation, EcoGoal contributes to large-scale data collection that would be difficult or impossible for professional scientists to achieve alone. The Ecogoal app is crucial in advancing environmental research and conservation efforts by bridging the gap between scientists and the public, leading to a better understanding of our planet and informed decision-making for a sustainable future.

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